

Analytical Applications of Bromamine-T

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THE present paper describes the use of naphthidine (N), 3,3'-dimethylnaphthidine disulphonic acid (DMNS), *o*-dianisidine (ODA), diphenylbenzidine (DB), quinoline yellow (QY), variamine blue (VB), α -naphthoflavone (NF), amaranth (Am), methyl red (MR) and methyl orange (MO) as redox indicators in the direct titration of arsenic(III), ascorbic acid (AA), hydroquinone (HQ), hydrazinium sulphate (HS), isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH), semicarbazide hydrochloride (SCH), phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (PHH) and hexacyanoferrate(II) with bromamine-T (BAT).

Experimental

All reagents used were of A.R. grade. Solutions (0.1%, w/v) of QY, VB, Am and MO in water, N in glacial acetic acid, DMNS in dilute ammonia¹, ODA in 0.5% sulphuric acid, NF and MR in ethanol and DB in conc. sulphuric acid were prepared. Approximately 0.05 *N* solutions of BAT, As(III), AA, HQ, HS, INH, SCH, PHH and hexacyanoferrate(II) were prepared and standardized by the accepted methods.

Potentiometric titrations : 20 ml of 0.05-0.02 *N* HQ, INH, SCH or hexacyanoferrate(II) and 10 ml of 10% potassium bromide (no bromide for HQ and INH) were diluted to 80 ml with sulphuric acid to give 1 *M* (0.5 *M* for SCH) and titrated potentiometrically with 0.05-0.02 *N* BAT solution.

Visual end-point titrations : 5-20 ml of 0.05-0.01 *N* As(III), AA, HQ, HS, INH, PHH or SCH or 5-10 ml hexacyanoferrate(II), 8 ml of 10% potassium bromide and X ml of 0.1% indicator were diluted to 40 ml with acid and titrated with 0.05-0.01 *N* BAT to the appearance or disappearance of a colour. The titration conditions, colour changes at the end-point and results are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The transition potentials of N, DMNS and ODA in the titration of HQ with BAT determined by the potentiometric method² vary between 778-771, 767-753 and 786-760 mV, respectively over the sulphuric acid concentration range of 0.5-2.5 *M*.

Potentiometric titrations : HQ, INH, SCH and hexacyanoferrate(II) have not been previously determined with BAT. We have now developed optimum conditions for the potentiometric titration of 0.05-0.02 *N* HQ, INH, SCH and hexacyanoferrate(II) with BAT. HQ was titrated in 1 *M* sulphuric acid solution containing no potassium bromide. The time required for the attainment of equilibrium potential is about 1 min and the potential jump is 230 mV with 0.1 ml of 0.02 *N* BAT. Increase in

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF As(III), AA, HQ, HS, INH, SCH, PHH AND HEXACYANOFERRATE(II) WITH BAT

Sl. No.	Reductant taken mg	Medium	Indicator	BAT (<i>N</i>)	Reductant determined* mg	Colour change at the end-point	Indicator required (X ml)
1. Arsenic(III)	88.45	0.8-1.5 <i>M</i> H ₂ SO ₄ (0.8-3 <i>M</i> for NF) or HCl or 2-3.5 <i>M</i> H ₂ PO ₄ + 0.4-4% KBr	DB NF	0.05	38.50	DB : Irreversible colourless to blue-violet.	0.8-1.2
	4.80	"		0.01	4.82	NF : Reversible pale green opalescence to rust brown	0.6-2.0
2. Ascorbic acid	87.72	0.5-1.5 <i>M</i> H ₂ SO ₄ or HCl or 2-4 <i>M</i> H ₂ PO ₄ (2-3.5 <i>M</i> for VB) + 0.4-5% KBr	N DMNS	0.05	87.64	N } Reversible DB } colourless VB } to violet	0.05-0.4 0.4-1.2
	2.86	1-3 <i>M</i> H ₂ PO ₄ (2- 3.5 <i>M</i> for VB) + 0.4-5% KBr	ODA DB VB	0.05	2.86	DMNS : Reversible colourless to pink ODA : Reversible colourless to orange-red	0.05-0.4 0.05-0.4
3. Hydroquinone	58.25	0.4-2.5 <i>M</i> H ₂ SO ₄ or 0.3-2 <i>M</i> HCl or 1.5-3 <i>M</i> H ₂ PO ₄ + 0.7-7% KBr	N DMNS ODA	0.05	53.32	N : Reversible light yellow to violet	0.1-0.5
	3.35	"		0.01	3.36	DMNS : Reversible light yellow to red ODA : Reversible light yellow to orange-red	0.1-0.5 0.1-0.5

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(Table 1 Contd.)

4. Hydrazinium sulphate	32.42	0.5-1.5 M H ₂ SO ₄ or HCl or 2-3.5 M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.4-4% KBr	DB	0.05	32.46	Irreversible colourless to violet	0.4-1.2
	2.85	"		0.01	2.86		
5. Isonicotinic acid hydrazide	35.07	0.4-1.3 M H ₂ SO ₄ or HCl + 0.5-4% KBr	QY Am MR MO	0.05	35.00	QY : Reversible yellow-green to colourless	0.6-1.5
	3.03	"		0.01	3.04	Am, MR, MO : Ir- reversible red to colourless	0.25-0.5
6. Semicarbazide hydrochloride	29.18	0.3-0.7 M H ₂ SO ₄ or 0.6-2 M HCl (0.4-1 M for MR or MO) or 2-3.5 M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.5-4% KBr	QY Am MR MO	0.05	29.24	"	"
	3.65	"		0.01	3.66		
7. Phenylhydrazine hydrochloride	37.81	0.2-0.6 M H ₂ SO ₄ or 0.8-1.5 M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.4-4% KBr	ODA Am MR MO	0.05	37.89	ODA : Reversible Am, MR, MO : Ir- reversible	0.1-0.5 0.1-0.5
	3.37	"		0.01	3.38		
8. Hexacyano-ferrate(II)	104.90	1-3 M HAc + 5-8 ml 10 M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.5-8% KBr	ODA	0.05	104.98	ODA : Reversible emerald green to orange-red	0.05-0.25
	6.09	"		0.01	6.12		

the concentration of sulphuric acid slightly decreases the potential jump of the system. The potential decreases in the presence of bromide.

INH was titrated potentiometrically in 0.4-1.3 M sulphuric acid solution containing no potassium bromide. The time required for the attainment of equilibrium potential is about 2 min and the potential jump is 460-270 mV with 0.1 ml of 0.02 N BAT. The effect of acid bromide is similar to that described for HQ.

SCH was titrated with BAT in 0.3-0.8 M sulphuric acid containing 0.8-5% potassium bromide. The time required for the attainment of equilibrium potential is about 2 min and the potential jump is 170 mV with 0.1 ml of 0.02 N BAT. Increase in the concentration of acid slightly increases the potential jump of the system. The absence of potassium bromide increases the time of attainment of equilibrium potential giving premature end-points.

The potentiometric titration of 0.05-0.2 N hexacyanoferrate(II) in 80 ml of 1-3 M acetic acid solution containing 5-8 ml of 10 M phosphoric acid and 0.4-1.5 g of potassium bromide gives a potential

jump of 100 mV with 0.1 ml of 0.02 N BAT. The presence of bromide is desirable as it gives accurate values and sharp potential jump. In the absence of bromide overtitration occurs. The presence of phosphoric acid reduces the time of attainment of equilibrium potential from 4 to 2 min.

Titration of ascorbic acid with BAT has been used for the determination of AA in vitamin C tablets and injections. The titration of INH has been used for the determination of INH in isoniazid tablets and syrup.

In the visual titration of the reductants, deviation from the permissible ranges of acidities, indicators and potassium bromide leads to sluggish, premature or late end-points.

References

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